

Supporting Information

Electronic properties and circuit applications of networks of electrochemically exfoliated 2D nanosheets

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Contents

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) of 2D Crystals	3
Mechanical Simulation: DFT calculations with vdW correction	7
Atomic Force Microscopy: EE of Elemental, TMM, TMD and TMTs	9
Raman Spectroscopy: Post-Transition Metal Monochalcogenides	11
Raman Spectroscopy: TMDs and Group IV (Post Transition Metal) Dichalcogenides	13
Raman Spectroscopy: Elemental 2D materials	15
Raman Spectroscopy: Transition Metal Trichalcogenides (TMT)	16
UV-Visible Optical Spectroscopy: Elemental 2D materials	17
UV-Visible Optical Spectroscopy: Post-Transition Metal Monochalcogenide	18
UV-Visible Optical Spectroscopy: Transition Metal Dichalcogenide	20
UV-Visible Optical Spectroscopy: Post Transition Metal Dichalcogenide	22
UV-Visible Optical Spectroscopy: Transition Metal Trichalcogenides	23
UV-Visible Optical Spectroscopy: Optical Bandgap Estimation	24
Selection of Nanosheets for Each 2D Material Family	25
Effect of Interlayer Spacing on Crystal Expansion.....	28
Solid-State Transistors: Indium Telluride and Gallium Telluride	30
Network Capacitance of Ionic Liquid Filled Networks	31
Ionic Current of Liquid Gated Transistors	34
Output Characteristics of Ionic Gated Transistors	35
Further Examination of Network Charge Carrier Densities	36
Terahertz Spectroscopy: Electrochemically Exfoliated Networks	37
Impedance Spectroscopy: Impedance of Semiconducting Nanosheet Networks	38
Impedance Spectroscopy: Measuring Contact Resistance of the Networks	39
Transfer Characteristics of FETs and NMOS	40
Measurement of circuit time constant τ	43
3-bit Digital-to-Analog Circuit	45
4-bit Digital-to-Analog Circuit	46
Amplitude Demodulation of BASK Signal.....	47
Literature Review of Solution Processed 2D Materials	49
Supplementary References	54

Supplementary Note 1 | X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) of 2D Crystals

X-ray diffraction (XRD) characterisation was performed for crystals prepared in-house. XRD for purchased crystals can be found at the respective manufacturing site. Measurements were taken with a Panalytical X'Pert Pro X-ray diffractometer fitted with a Cu tube emitting K_{α} radiation at a wavelength of 1.5406 Å. The samples were prepared by grinding crystals using a mortar and pestle and pressing the resulting powder on a glass slide. 2θ diffraction patterns were recorded and the primary peaks were indexed by comparison with reference data from the ICDD PDF-2 database.¹ The raw data, which is sufficient for indexing, is shown below without any additional peak fitting or refinement. A preferred orientation was exhibited by each sample such that enhanced diffraction was observed from planes parallel to the layers in the crystal structure. This is typical for powders of 2D layered crystals and indicates that the particles had a 2D-like platelet morphology, with the long side preferentially aligning with the substrate.²

Supplementary Figure 1. XRD spectra for Monochalcogenides GeS (left), GeSe (center), and InTe (right). The strong (004) peaks in GeS and GeSe are consistent with the preferred orientation of the lattice planes of the nanosheets along the glass substrate. InTe appears to show less preferred orientation. The relative intensities of the (221), (220), and (202) peaks suggest the presence of two InTe polymorphs: InTe(I) and InTe(II), of which the latter can only be obtained *via* high pressure³, which is possible using the methods used in this work (see methods section).

Supplementary Figure 2. XRD spectra for pure phase dichalcogenides MoS₂ (left), WS₂ (center), and WSe₂ (right). The strong (002), (004), (006), and (008) peaks are consistent with the preferred orientation of the lattice planes of the nanosheets along the glass substrate.

Supplementary Figure 3. XRD spectra for pure doped dichalcogenides Mo_{1-x}Se₂:Nb_x (left) and W_{1-x}Se₂:Nb_x (center) and alloyed dichalcogenide Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ (right). The strong (002), (004), (006), and (008) peaks are consistent with the preferred orientation of the lattice planes of the nanosheets along the glass substrate. Importantly, for both the doped samples (left and centre), no pure phase NbS₂ is observed. Furthermore, as shown in the left panel, the peak locations are essentially identical to pure MoSe₂, which is consistent with atomic doping. This is in contrast to alloying, where the peak locations should be located clearly between the two pure materials and linearly according to Vegard's law for alloys⁴. For the alloyed sample (right panel), no pure phase material peaks are observed, indicating successful alloying.

Supplementary Figure 4. XRD spectra for dichalcogenides PdSe₂ (left), PtSe₂ (center) and TaS₂ (right). For PdSe₂, the strong (002) peak is consistent with the preferred orientation of the lattice plate along the glass substrate. For PtSe₂ the strong (001) peak is in accordance with preferred orientation. For TaS₂, the strong (002), (004), (006), and (008) peaks are consistent with the preferred orientation of the lattice planes of the nanosheets along the glass substrate.

Supplementary Figure 5. XRD spectra for dichalcogenides SnSe₂ (left) and MoTe₂ (center) and trichalcogenide HfSe₃ (right). For SnSe₂, the strong peak at (001) is consistent with the preferred orientation along the lattice plane of the nanoplatelet. For MoTe₂, strong peaks at (002), (004), (008) are consistent with the preferred orientation. Due to the lack of available experimental data on layered HfSe₃, this material was not able to be reliably indexed. However, the peak located around 14° indicates a clear preferred orientation of the nanosheets along the glass substrate, confirming the layered nature of the material. Reference data for an HfSe₃ powder (note, not nanoplatelets) is shown for comparison.

Supplementary Figure 6. XRD spectra for triphosphates CoPS₃ (left), FePS₃ (center), and NiPS₃ (right). The strong (001), (002), and (004) peaks are consistent with the preferred orientation of the lattice planes of the nanosheets along the glass substrate.

Supplementary Note 2 | Mechanical Simulation: DFT calculations with vdW correction

Material	E_b (meV \AA^{-2})	C_{11}	C_{22}	C_{12}	C_{33}	E_{IN} (GPa)	E_{OUT} (GPa)	E_{IN}/E_{OUT}
TMT								
FePS ₃	25.5	120	121	34	28	110	28	3.89
NiPS ₃	20.6	1340*	1350*	380*	441*	124*	44*	2.81
HfSe ₃	20.3	126	100	14	49	111	49	2.28
CoPS ₃	24.7	1543*	1534*	502*	461*	1375*	461*	2.98
TMD								
MoS ₂	28.7	205	205	54	37	191	37	5.18
WS ₂	22.7	233	233	55	49	220	49	4.53
WSe ₂	22.6	1995*	1995*	404*	526*	191*	53*	3.64
WSe ₂ :Nb	22.6	1995	1995	404	526	191	53	3.64
MoSe ₂	20.4	167	167	46	37	155	37	4.16
MoSe ₂ :Nb	20.4	167	167	46	37	155	37	4.16
PtSe ₂	29.6	167	167	54	30	149	30	5.00
SnSe ₂	17.3	95	95	28	27	87	27	3.27
TaS ₂	22.3	192	192	66	45	170	45	3.78
MoTe ₂	24.5	120	120	33	41	110	41	2.68
Mo _{0.5} W _{0.5} Se ₂	23*	2008*	2008*	388*	708*	1933*	708*	2.73
PdSe ₂	26.78*	1309*	1297*	874*	1296*	72*	130*	0.55
TMM								
InSe	14.91	629	629	199	329	57	33	1.72
GaTe	15.7	70	30	19	60	38	60	0.62
SnS	36.2	97	51	42	82	45	82	0.55
SnSe	35.3*	81	53	7	74	64	74	0.87
InTe	38.5*	35	35	14	55	30	55	0.54
TlSe	38.73	40	40	17	65	33	65	0.52
GeSe	36	162	162	7	162	162	162	1.00
GeS	37.3	107	55	2	101	76	101	0.75
Elemental								
BP	38.43	185	57	6	54	102	54	1.90
Te	22.92*	30	30	8	60	28	60	0.47
Ge	89.97	108	108	41	108	93	108	0.86
BCT								
Bi ₂ O ₂ Se	77	156	156	73	121	121	121	1.00

Supplementary Table 1: **Binding energy and mechanical properties of crystals by DFT:** Binding energy and elastic constants from MC2D and JARVIS database, respectively.^{5,6} Data marked with * are calculated by our own DFT simulations with vdW correction. Data for Bi₂O₂Se is taken from the literature.⁷

The ratio of in-plane (E_{in}) and out-of-plane (E_{out}) Young's moduli has previously been used to measure exploitability for LPE 2D materials based on the assumption of energy equipartition.⁸ The larger the E_{in}/E_{out} ratio, the easier a bulk crystal can be exfoliated into a 2D material. To accelerate the calculation of Young's moduli, we use the Joint Automated Repository for Various Integrated Simulations (JARVIS) database to find the elastic constants related to the material's response to stress in each crystal.^{5,6} The elastic constants (C_{11} , C_{22} , C_{12} , and C_{33}) in the database are obtained using density functional theory (DFT) with van der Waals (vdW) corrections considered to provide more accurate material properties. When the vdW direction is

oriented along the z-axis, the out-of-plane Young's modulus E_{out} is denoted by the elastic constant C_{33} . The in-plane Young's modulus E_{in} can be calculated by,

$$E_{\text{in}} = \frac{C_{11}C_{22} - C_{12}^2}{\sqrt{C_{11}C_{22}}} \quad (2)$$

Another measure previously used to predict the exfoliability of 2D materials is the binding energy, E_{b} , defined as the difference between the ground-state energy of the relaxed 3D bulk structure and all of its unrelaxed substructures of any dimensionality per unit area.^{9,10} Previous DFT work categorised materials with binding energy below $120 \text{ meV } \text{\AA}^{-2}$ as potentially exploitable, and materials that have higher binding energies are non-exfoliative.¹⁰ We use the materials cloud database to determine E_{b} of each material presented in Supplementary Table 1.

Materials which did not have sufficient information in the database were simulated within the DFT framework using the Quantum ESPRESSO package^{11,12} and the v1.1 SSSP efficiency pseudopotentials' library¹³. We employed the Perdew, Burke and Ernzerhof's (PBE)¹⁴ parametrisation of the generalised gradient approximation (GGA) to describe the exchange-correlation effect of electrons. The vdW functionals at the vdw-df2-c09¹⁵ and rVV10¹⁶ levels were adopted for non-magnetic and magnetic materials, respectively, according to previously described protocols.⁹ All simulations were performed with the suggested plane-wave energy cutoff of the SSSP library and a k-point density of 0.15 \AA^{-1} , and a Marzari–Vanderbilt cold smearing¹⁷ of 0.02 Ry was further used to converge the Brillouin zone integral in metallic systems. For elastic constant calculations, we used the finite difference of the strain-stress relation as implemented in thermo_pw code,¹⁸ where the independent strains with a magnitude of 0.005 were applied to deform the system depending on the Laue class and crystal symmetry. The elastic stiffness tensor was then calculated as the first-order derivative of stress with respect to strain.

Supplementary Figure 7: Atomic force microscopy of 2D material nanosheets. a-d Lateral size (L) and apparent thickness (t) of the elemental, monochalcogenide, dichalcogenide and trichalcogenide 2D nanosheets. e-h Aspect ratio (i.e. L/t) of the elemental, monochalcogenide, dichalcogenide and trichalcogenide 2D nanosheets.

Supplementary Figure 8: Predicted crystal mechanical properties combined with atomic force microscopy for each material. a Lateral size (L), b apparent thickness (t) and c nanosheet aspect ratio (AR) of the elemental, monochalcogenide, dichalcogenide and trichalcogenide 2D nanosheets as a function of the ratio of in-plane young's modulus to out-of-plane young's modulus. Error is calculated by SDOM, for each material $n = 25$, except for SnSe, InTe, $FePS_3$ where $n = 35, 52, 45$ and respectively and the TMD's $Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se_2$, $WSe_2:Nb$ and WSe_2 , which have $n = 33$.

Material	<L> (nm)	<t> (nm)	<AR>
BP	2477 ± 303	7 ± 1	456 ± 81
Tellurene	294 ± 24	43 ± 4	9 ± 1
GaTe	207 ± 15	79 ± 6	3 ± 1
InSe	1971 ± 206	4.0 ± 0.2	531 ± 74
InTe	589 ± 43	95 ± 5	6 ± 1
SnS	131 ± 31	14 ± 1	20 ± 9
SnSe	412 ± 43	23 ± 2	25 ± 8
MoSe₂	1937 ± 232	10 ± 1	250 ± 35
MoSe₂:Nb	1683 ± 285	10 ± 1	212 ± 43
WSe₂	549 ± 48	9 ± 1	67 ± 6
WSe₂:Nb	1598 ± 321	5 ± 1	303 ± 57
MoS₂	1230 ± 196	11 ± 1	117 ± 20
Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂	1851 ± 211	14 ± 1	188 ± 33
PtSe₂	1960 ± 325	6 ± 1	370 ± 78
WS₂	1818 ± 146	7 ± 1	347 ± 55
MoTe₂	1942 ± 192	10 ± 1	233 ± 32
SnSe₂	1576 ± 152	10 ± 1	171 ± 21
TaS₂	1414 ± 148	3.0 ± 0.2	600 ± 115
NiPS₃	4988 ± 842	4.0 ± 0.3	2084 ± 448
CoPS₃	2467 ± 409	15 ± 1	198 ± 33
FePS₃	1643 ± 147	12 ± 1	160 ± 16
HfSe₃	4268 ± 376	12 ± 1	473 ± 72

Supplementary Table 2: Summary of atomic force microscopy results. Average lateral size <L>, average apparent thickness <t> and average aspect ratio <AR> for each of the elemental (red), monochalcogenide (blue), dichalcogenide (orange) and trichalcogenide (green) 2D nanosheets. Error is calculated by SDOM, for each material n = 25, except for SnSe, InTe, FePS₃ where n = 35, 52, 45 and respectively and the TMD's Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂, WSe₂:Nb and WSe₂ which have n = 33.

Supplementary Figure 9: Raman spectroscopy of post-transition metal monochalcogenides. **a** Raman spectroscopy of the PTMM materials. **b** Raman spectra of the SnSe starting bulk crystal (brown) and the exfoliated SnSe nanosheets (black) **c** Raman spectra of the SnS starting bulk crystal (black) and the electrochemically exfoliated SnS nanosheet (yellow).

Supplementary Figure 9a (yellow curve) shows that the vibrational modes of the A_{1g}, E_{2g} and A_{1g} are found at ~117, 180 and 228 cm⁻¹, respectively, indicative of few-layer InSe. The A_{1g} mode is associated with the out-of-plane vibrations of the Se atoms, while the E_{2g} mode is due to in-plane vibrations between the In and Se in the basal plane.¹⁹ Supplementary Figure 9a (blue curve) shows the two expected vibrational modes at 122 (A_{1g}) and 141 cm⁻¹ (E_g) for indium telluride (InTe).²⁰ Very little has been investigated regarding the raman vibrational modes of InTe, the A_{1g} mode is likely associated with the out-of-plane vibrations of the Te atoms and the E_g mode associated with the in-plane vibrations between the In and Te atoms, similar to the other group III monochalcogenides.

Supplementary Figure 9a (black curve) shows the Raman spectra of the gallium telluride (GaTe) sample, which shows the A_g vibrational mode at 124 cm⁻¹.²¹ Unlike freshly cleaved GaTe, which has additional peaks >150 cm⁻¹.²² The peak at 143 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the surface's adsorbed oxygen (GaTe-O₂).²² We exfoliated our GaTe in a glovebox and used degassed solvents to exfoliate. However, the oxygen could have been adsorbed during the Raman measurement in the air or small quantities of O₂ <0.1 ppm could have been adsorbed over time while stored in the glove box. The InTe, GaTe and InSe spectra are consistent with measurements on liquid-phase exfoliated nanosheets.²⁰

We undertook an additional Raman spectroscopy investigation on the tin-based group IV monochalcogenides since they can exist in various phases and polytypes due to the different oxidation states of Sn and consequently have vastly different electronic properties.²³ In Supplementary Figure 9b, the SnSe crystal before exfoliation shows B_{3g} and A_g peaks (brown curve) associated with the semiconducting p_{nma} phase of the SnSe crystal. After electrochemical exfoliation (black curve), the phase of the material changes to the

semimetallic bmm phase, which is attributed to the quenching of the B_{3g} mode and upshift of the A_g peak to 236 cm^{-1} .²⁴

We also investigated tin sulfide (SnS) nanosheets in Supplementary Figure 9c and found the prominent A_g and B_{3g} modes expected for SnS crystals.²³ Once exfoliated the A_g peak increases in intensity and shifts to 246 cm^{-1} and has an absence of the B_{3g} peak which is indicative of SnS with an armchair configuration rather than zigzag.²⁵ Therefore, the pnma phase is retained.²⁶

Supplementary Note 5 | Raman Spectroscopy: Transition Metal Dichalcogenides and Group IV (Post Transition Metal) Dichalcogenides

Supplementary Figure 10: Raman spectroscopy of Transition Metal Dichalcogenides and Group IV (Post Transition Metal) Dichalcogenides. a,b Raman spectroscopy of the TMD's c Raman spectra of the niobium doped TMDs d. Raman spectra of SnSe₂ a post transitional metal dichalcogenide. The spectra in all cases are consistent with reports of the semiconducting 2H phase and the J1, J2 or J3 vibrational modes attributed to the metallic 1T phases are not observed. We mark the absent peaks with a star (*).

Next, we investigated the phase and quality of the transition metal and group IV dichalcogenides used in the study. Supplementary Figure 10a depicts the spectra of the MoS₂ (black), MoSe₂ (yellow), WSe₂ (blue) and the alloy Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ (green) nanosheets after drop casting and annealing at 120 °C on Si/SiO₂. The black MoS₂ spectrum (Supplementary Figure 10a, black curve) shows the typical E_{2g} and A_{1g} peaks at 385 cm⁻¹ and 412 cm⁻¹, respectively.^{27,28} The Raman spectrum of the MoSe₂ (Supplementary Figure 10a, yellow curve) has two peaks located at ~ 245 and 287 cm⁻¹ attributed to the A_{1g} and E_{2g} Raman modes.²⁹

The WSe₂ (Supplementary Figure 10a, blue curve) has a peak at ($\sim 251 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) attributed to the A_{1g} and E_{2g} Raman modes, indicating the formation of few-layer nanosheets.^{30,31} Our Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ has a ratio of 0.5:0.5 (Mo:W). In Supplementary Figure 10a, (green curve) we find the A_{1g} vibrational mode at $\sim 247 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to the out of plane motion of the Se atoms relative to a Mo or W atom and a weak E_{2g} vibration at $\sim 146 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to the in-plane vibrational motion of the Se atoms.³²

The Raman spectrum of the WS₂ (Supplementary Figure 10b, black) also matches the previous literature reports for few-layer WS₂, having an A_{1g} peak ($\sim 421 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and an overlapping 2LA and E_{2g} peak at 354 cm^{-1} .³³ The Raman spectrum of the MoTe₂ nanosheets are shown in Supplementary Figure 10b, yellow curve and demonstrate in-plane vibrational modes (E_{2g}) at $\sim 235 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a B_{2g} at $\sim 290 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The presence of the B_{2g} mode indicates that we have few layer MoTe₂,³⁴ since the B_{2g} mode is not observed in bulk.³⁵

For the MoS₂, MoSe₂, MoTe₂ WS₂ and WSe₂, the J₂ and J₃ vibrational modes attributed to the metallic 1T phase are not observed.³⁶⁻⁴¹ We plot the Raman spectra for PtSe₂ in Supplementary Figure 10b, blue curve. We observe the A_{1g} and E_g peaks at $\sim 207 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 180 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The E_g peak arises due to the vibration of selenium (Se) atoms within the plane, while the A_{1g} peak results from the vibration of Se atoms perpendicular to the plane.⁴² The intensity ratio of A_{1g}/E_g is ~ 0.2 and consistent with the ratio expected for ultra-thin $<3 \text{ nm}$ PtSe₂.⁴³ Similarly the peak positions of the A_{1g} and E_g modes would suggest nanosheets that are $<5 \text{ nm}$.⁴⁴ These results are consistent with our AFM results (main text), which show an apparent thickness of $\sim 3 \text{ nm}$ due to the favourable mechanical properties of PtSe₂ for electrochemical exfoliation.

The Raman spectra of TaS₂ are plotted in Supplementary Figure 10b, green. We observe the E_{1g}, E_{2g} and A_{1g} vibrational modes at $\sim 244, 301$ and 385 cm^{-1} respectively. The E_{1g} modes represent the in-plane vibrations of the Se atoms, while the E_{2g} mode represents the in-plane vibrations of the S and Ta atoms. The A_{1g} mode represents the out-of-plane vibration of the S atoms.⁴⁵ The peak positions of the vibrational modes are consistent with what would be expected for 2H-TaS₂,⁴⁶

We undertake Raman spectroscopy of the niobium-doped TMD's WSe₂ and MoSe₂ in Supplementary Figure 3c. We don't observe any differences between the doped WSe₂ and MoSe₂ and their undoped counterparts. This is not unexpected since metals do not typically have observable Raman peaks.⁴⁷

Next, we examine SnSe₂ by raman spectroscopy which is a post-transition metal dichalcogenide. We observe the in-plane E_g vibrational mode at $\sim 111 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the out-of-plane A_{1g} vibrational mode at $\sim 186 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ consistent with previous reports.⁴⁸ 2H-SnSe₂ the E_g peak is located at 108 cm^{-1} (in theory) while 1T-SnSe₂, gives rise to an upshift of the E_g peak to $\sim 119 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.^{48,49} Therefore we have electrochemically exfoliated the 2H-SnSe₂ phase.

Supplementary Figure 11: Raman spectroscopy of the elemental 2D materials electrochemically exfoliated. Raman spectroscopy of the elemental 2D materials black phosphorus and tellurene labelled with their corresponding vibrational modes.

We examine the Raman spectra of the elemental 2D materials in Supplementary Figure 11. Black Phosphorus (BP) (black curve) shows the A^1_g , B^2_g and A^2_g vibrational modes at 360, 435 and 465 cm^{-1} respectively. The A^2_g and B^2_g modes are related to in-plane vibrations of the phosphorus and the A^1_g mode is related to the out-of-plane movement of the phosphorus.⁵⁰ The peak positions are upshifted compared to bulk BP samples, which have A^1_g and A^2_g vibrational modes at 359 and 463 cm^{-1} which suggests the BP nanosheets are thin with nanosheet thickness <10 nm,⁵¹ consistent with our AFM results presented in the main text.

Next, we examine our tellurene nanosheets in Supplementary Figure 11 (yellow curve) and find the A_1 (124 cm^{-1}) and E_2 (144 cm^{-1}) vibrational modes, which are typical of tellurene and attributed to Te atoms moving in the basal plane (A_1) and asymmetric stretching (E_2) of Te atoms.⁵² The presence of the E_2 mode would suggest that the nanosheets are >20 nm thick (consistent with our AFM results), which is not active for monolayer or few-layer nanosheets.⁵³

Supplementary Figure 12: Raman spectroscopy of the electrochemically exfoliated transition metal trichalcogenide and layered metal phosphorus trichalcogenides. Iron phosphorus trisulfide, cobalt phosphorus trisulfide, nickel phosphorus trisulfide and hafnium triselenide are labelled with their corresponding vibrational modes.

We undertake raman of the transition metal trichalcogenides and layered metal phosphorus trichalcogenides in Supplementary Figure 12. The Raman spectroscopy of hafnium triselenide (HfSe₃) (green curve) shows a A_g peaks at 202 cm⁻¹, 232 cm⁻¹ and 253 cm⁻¹ which are likely attributed to the A_g vibrational mode.⁵⁴ Iron phosphorus trisulfide (FePS₃) spectra (yellow curve) show Raman peaks at 280 cm⁻¹ and 384 cm⁻¹ which are attributed to the A_g and B_g vibrational modes.⁵⁵ Nickle phosphorus trisulfide (NiPS₃) spectra (blue) show one peak at 236 cm⁻¹ attributed to the out-of-plane A_g vibrational mode. As the layer number in NiPS₃ increases from monolayers to bulk, the Raman active peaks increase in intensity,⁵⁶ which has previously been attributed to constructive interference enhancement.⁵⁶ Cobalt phosphorus trisulfide (CoPS₃) spectra (black curve) display a single peak at 382 cm⁻¹ which is expected for ultra-thin CoPS₃ nanosheets and is attributed to the A_g vibrational mode.⁵⁷

Supplementary Figure 13: UV-visible optical absorption spectra of the electrochemically exfoliated elemental 2D materials. a UV-vis spectra of black phosphorus and **b** tellurene with the characteristic absorption peaks shown.

Supplementary Figure 13 presents a selection of the UV-visible optical absorption for black phosphorus (BP) obtained using an integrating sphere where we have subtracted the scattering component of each spectrum from the extinction spectra to obtain the absorption spectra.⁵⁸ We observe a broad absorption band across the UV and NIR wavelengths, which is consistent with previous reports for BP nanosheets made by LPE.⁵⁹ There is also a characteristic absorption peak at ~ 620 nm, which has not previously been observed. Figure 1b shows the spectra of tellurene and reveals an excitonic transition at 348 nm attributed to the transition of valence band p-orbital charge carriers to the conduction band.⁶⁰

Supplementary Figure 14: UV-visible optical absorption spectra of the electrochemically exfoliated Post-Transition Metal Monochalcogenides. a UV-vis spectra of indium selenide, **b** indium telluride and **c** gallium telluride with the characteristic absorption peaks shown.

Supplementary Figure 14 presents the UV-visible optical absorption for indium selenide (InSe), which shows a broad peak at ~ 260 nm, which is consistent with the expected peak position from DFT calculations.⁶¹ Supplementary Figure 14b shows the spectra obtained for indium telluride (InTe) it is a characteristic absorption peak at ~ 342 nm, which is consistent with DFT calculations for the expected peaks.⁶¹ Supplementary Figure 14c shows the spectra obtained for gallium telluride (GaTe), which shows a characteristic absorption peak at ~ 324 nm, the featureless tail is consistent with previous reports.⁶²

Supplementary Figure 15: UV-visible optical absorption spectra of the electrochemically exfoliated tin-based metal monochalcogenides. a UV-vis spectra of tin sulfide and **b** tin selenide with the characteristic absorption peaks shown.

Supplementary Figure 15a presents the UV-visible optical absorption for tin sulfide (SnS), which shows a broad absorption that extends from 270 nm to 480 nm, which is consistent with previous reports.⁶³ The scattering background is also small at wavelengths above 600 nm, suggesting the presence of small nanosheets, consistent with our AFM data in the main text. Supplementary Figure 15b presents the UV-visible optical absorption for tin selenide (SnSe), which shows a broad absorption that extends from 270 nm to 480 nm, which is also consistent with previous reports.⁶⁴ Similar to the SnS nanosheet, the SnSe had a small scattering component >450 nm, which is attributed to the size of the nanosheets.

Supplementary Figure 16: UV-visible optical absorption spectra of the electrochemically exfoliated transition metal dichalcogenides. **a** UV-vis spectra tungsten diselenide (WSe_2), **b** molybdenum disulfide (MoS_2), **c** molybdenum diselenide (MoSe_2), **d** tungsten disulfide (WS_2), **e** molybdenum tungsten diselenide ($\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$), **f** molybdenum ditelluride (MoTe_2) with the extinction, absorption and scattering components of the UV-vis spectra shown in black, brown and blue for each material respectively. In Supplementary Figure 16a-f, UV-visible optical absorption spectra of the WSe_2 , MoS_2 , MoSe_2 , WS_2 , MoTe_2 , and $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ inks are taken with an integrating sphere to isolate the extinction, absorption and scattering components of the TMD inks.⁵⁸ The excitonic peak positions of the materials are consistent with previous reports for well-known TMD's displaying the A and B excitons WSe_2 , MoS_2 , MoSe_2 , WS_2 and MoTe_2 and are consistent with previous reports.^{34,65-67} The $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ spectra show excitonic peaks that are similar to MoSe_2 that correspond to the A and B excitons at 798 nm and 658 nm, respectively.⁶⁶ In all cases, the scattering component is large and $\sim 50\%$ of the extinction spectra intensity, which would suggest a large nanosheet L . The ratio of the extinction at the B exciton peak (Ext_B) to the local minimum at 345 nm (Ext_{345}) in the MoS_2 spectral analysis (refer to Supplementary Figure 16b, black curve) serves as a metric for determining L .⁵⁸ The $\text{Ext}_B/\text{Ext}_{345} > 1$ indicates that the nanosheets are large with $L > 400$ nm.⁵⁸ Similarly, the length L of WS_2 , MoSe_2 and WSe_2 can be gauged by the ratio of extinction at the A exciton peak (Ext_A) to the local minimum. For WS_2 the local minimum is found at 295 nm ($\text{Ext}_A/\text{Ext}_{295}$).⁵⁸ We find $\text{Ext}_A/\text{Ext}_{295} > 1$

indicating $L > 400$ nm.^{58,68} For MoSe₂ and WSe₂ the extinction at 365 nm and 334 nm can be used to indicate we have larger sized nanosheets with $Ext_A/Ext_{365} > 0.4$ and $Ext_A/Ext_{334} > 0.22$ respectively.⁵⁸ The size metrics determined by UV-vis are in agreement with our AFM statistics from the main text.

Supplementary Figure 17: UV-visible optical absorption spectra of the electrochemically exfoliated transition metal dichalcogenides. a UV-vis spectra platinum diselenide (PtSe₂) **b** tantalum disulfide (TaS₂) **c** MoSe₂ doped with Nb, and **d** WSe₂ doped with Nb. The extinction, absorption and scattering components of the UV-vis spectra are shown in black, brown and blue for each material, respectively.

In Supplementary Figure 17a the spectra for PtSe₂ exhibit a broad absorption range with two peaks around 616 nm and 398 nm, respectively. The greater intensity of the 616 nm peak implies that the nanosheet is thin < 5 nm (consistent with our AFM) and consistent with the peaks expected from the literature.⁶⁹ The absorption is high $\sim 50\%$ of the extinction signal at IR wavelengths, which would suggest that there are thicker nanosheets in the dispersion, which are semi-metallic rather than semiconducting like PtSe₂ monolayers.⁶⁹ The spectra of TaS₂ show absorption peak positions at 390 nm and 626 nm, which is consistent with a previous report with LPE nanosheets for UV wavelengths.⁷⁰ There is almost no scattering background at wavelengths above 650 nm, and there is strong absorption at wavelengths > 600 nm, the lack of an absorption band edge would imply metallic behaviour in the material. There are no previous reports on the optical properties of the Nb-doped WSe₂ and MoSe₂ materials shown in Supplementary Figure 17c-d. But the peak positions and optical properties are the same as their undoped counterparts.

Supplementary Figure 18: UV-visible optical absorption spectra of the electrochemically exfoliated post-TMD. a UV-vis spectra of tin diselenide (SnSe₂) with the characteristic absorption peaks shown.

The UV-vis spectra for the post-TMD SnSe₂ is shown in Supplementary Figure 18. The spectra are featureless and is consistent with previous reports.⁷¹ The high intensity in the IR wavelengths would imply metallic behaviour. All of the TMDs have strong absorption at shorter wavelengths (430 nm) due to interband transitions.⁷²

Supplementary Figure 19: UV-visible optical absorption spectra of the electrochemically exfoliated TMTs. a UV-vis spectra of iron phosphorus trichalcogenide (FePS_3), **b** cobalt phosphorus trichalcogenide (CoPS_3), **c** nickel phosphorus trichalcogenide (NiPS_3) and **d** hafnium triselenide (HfSe_3) with the characteristic absorption peaks shown.

Supplementary Figure 19 shows the extinction, absorption and scattering components of UV-visible optical absorption spectra for the TMTs. Iron phosphorus trichalcogenide (FePS_3) shows no prominent absorption peaks and stronger absorption at wavelengths <450 nm, consistent with a previous study.⁷³ Similarly, the cobalt phosphorus trichalcogenide (CoPS_3) spectra, shown in Supplementary Figure 19b, are mostly featureless, with a weak absorption peak found at ~ 216 nm. To our knowledge there are no other reports on this material reporting its optical properties. The spectra for nickel phosphorus trichalcogenide (NiPS_3) is shown in Supplementary Figure 19c and show characteristic absorption peaks at 218 nm, 352 nm, and 528 nm, consistent with a previous report.⁷⁴ In Supplementary Figure 19d we obtain the spectra of hafnium triselenide (HfSe_3) and observe absorption peaks at 444 and 514 nm. To our knowledge, the optical properties of HfSe_3 nanosheets have not previously been examined. However, it is possible that the peaks are related to the excitation of the charge carriers in the Se p-orbital valence states to the conduction band.⁷⁵

Supplementary Figure 20: Tauc plots. **a** Tauc plot of the elemental inks. **b** Tauc plot of the TMM inks. **c** Tauc plot of the TMD inks. **d** Tauc plot of the TMT inks.

We find the optical bandgap for each of the 2D inks in Supplementary Figure 20 with Tauc plots. By using the absorption data from UV-vis spectra, the optical bandgap (E_{Op}) of the semiconductor can be calculated by extrapolating a straight line of the $(\alpha h\nu)^{0.5}$ at the absorption band edge and assuming that we have indirect transitions.⁷⁶ The E_{Op} will be slightly less than the semiconductor bandgap as it doesn't account for the excitonic band gap⁷⁷ however it provides a good estimate for comparative study.

Supplementary Figure 21: **a** AFM micrograph showing InSe nanosheets drop-cast onto a Si/SiO₂ substrate. **b-c** Nanosheet lateral size, L , (**b**) and aspect ratio, AR, (**c**) plotted versus apparent nanosheet thickness, t , for four selected nanosheet types. Each data point represents a single nanosheet. **d** Relationship between average nanosheet lateral size ($\langle L \rangle$) and apparent thickness ($\langle t \rangle$) for each material under study. The data has been grouped into families of materials: TMT, TMD, TMM, and elemental materials. **e** Dependence of mean nanosheet AR for each material on the starting crystal's E_{in}/E_{out} ratio. The data has been grouped into material families, as shown in **d**. **f** Scanning electron microscopy images showing the morphology of solution-deposited nanosheet networks prepared using nanosheets from each material family. These images show alignment and connectivity for high AR nanosheets and the presence of nanoparticles and nanorods in the tellurene network. **g** Raman spectra of selected 2D materials showing characteristic vibrational modes, indicating the phase and quality of exfoliated nanosheets. **h** UV-visible optical absorption spectra of tellurene, InSe, Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂, and HfSe₃ nanosheets, revealing their optical properties and excitonic peaks.

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) is utilised to determine the lateral size, L and observed nanosheet apparent thickness, t of nanosheets in the inks made from elemental, TMM, TMD and TMT materials. In Supplementary Figure 21, we improve the clarity of the presented data by presenting one material from each family studied, tellurene, InSe, Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ and HfSe₃. An AFM micrograph showing InSe nanosheets that are drop-cast onto a Si/SiO₂ substrate are shown in Supplementary Figure 21a, displaying average nanosheet lateral size, $\langle L \rangle \sim 2.0 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ and average nanosheet apparent thickness, $\langle t \rangle \sim 4.0 \pm 0.2 \text{ nm}$.

Supplementary Figure 21b illustrates the relationship between $\langle L \rangle$ and $\langle t \rangle$ for tellurene, InSe, Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ and HfSe₃ nanosheets, showing no direct link, a contrast to what is observed for nanosheets produced via liquid phase exfoliation (LPE), where $\langle L \rangle$ will increase with $\langle t \rangle$.⁸ The $\langle L \rangle$ are measured to be $0.29 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{m}$ for tellurene, $2 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ for InSe, $1.9 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ for Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ and $0.67 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{m}$ for HfSe₃. Meanwhile, $\langle t \rangle$ is found to be $43 \pm 4 \text{ nm}$ for tellurene, $4.0 \pm 0.2 \text{ nm}$ for InSe, $14 \pm 1 \text{ nm}$ for Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ and $12 \pm 1 \text{ nm}$ for HfSe₃. When the AR, ($L t^{-1}$) is plotted against t , as shown in Supplementary Figure 21c, the maximum AR values recorded were ~ 1000 for InSe, Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ and HfSe₃ and $AR < 100$ for tellurene. To enable the highest possible device performances an $AR > 40$ is considered necessary to facilitate nanosheet-to-nanosheet connections with minimised R_J .⁷⁸ Therefore InSe, Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ and HfSe₃ will make nice conformal networks once deposited. LS deposition can help to align the nanosheets⁷⁹ however, once the $AR > 40$, the nanosheets self-align their basal plane parallel to the substrate, even if the inks are drop-cast.⁸⁰ Supplementary Figure 21d summarises the $\langle L \rangle$ and $\langle t \rangle$ found for each 2D nanosheet ink. For each material family, $\langle L \rangle$ is not strongly correlated to $\langle t \rangle$, which is unique to EE nanosheet production. The trend is unexpected as traditional LPE exfoliation techniques such as ultrasonication, shear mixing or microfluidization would show a strong correlation of increasing $\langle L \rangle$ with $\langle t \rangle$, which can be attributed to the interplay of matching hasan solubility parameters and the mechanical action of the exfoliation process which favours larger and thicker nanosheets.⁸¹ In contrast, the EE is producing nanosheets where $\langle L \rangle$ is not increasing with $\langle t \rangle$, likely due to the nature of the EE exfoliation mechanism where once ion intercalation overcomes E_b , exfoliation is likely, and then the resulting nanosheet geometry is largely dependet on the crystal mechanical properties and post-expansion size selection protocols rather than the mechanical or chemical force applied. In Supplementary Figure 21e, we show how $\langle AR \rangle$ depends on the starting crystals E_{in}/E_{out} for each material family. It is observed that once the E_{in}/E_{out} is > 1.7 , the nanosheet $AR > 500$, which is independent of the family of 2D material. Furthermore, if $E_{in}/E_{out} < 1$, the AR is less than 25, which is not a sufficient AR to make conformal nanosheet-to-nanosheet junctions for high-performance devices.⁷⁸

In Supplementary Figure 21f, we examine a selection of networks from each material family by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to assess the nanosheets' morphology when assembled in a network. In materials such as InSe, MoWSe and HfSe₃, where the nanosheet AR is high (>100), the network reveals well-aligned and seamless connections between nanosheets, suggesting low R_J .⁷⁸ Additionally, the presence of folds and wrinkles in the nanosheets indicates a high degree of nanosheet flexibility, which is expected since our AFM results indicate low apparent thickness ($<10 \text{ nm}$) in these materials. In Figure 2f, we observe a nonconformal and misaligned tellurene network. We attribute the misalignment of the nanosheets to their low aspect ratio (<40) since the network has a similar morphology to what is typically seen in low AR LPE networks.⁷⁸ Rods are also observed in the network previously observed in solution phase synthesis of tellurene.⁸² The co-existence of tellurene nanowires with nanosheets has previously been observed during the growth of tellurene nanosheets. The formation of tellurene nanowires is energetically preferred for the Te atoms. It is possible that

the electrochemical exfoliation of the bulk telluride provides a combination of both 1D and 2D dimensionalities.⁸³

We use Raman spectroscopy with a 532 nm laser to identify the phase and quality of the 2D nanosheets after exfoliation. Supplementary Figure 21g depicts select spectra from each material family being examined. Tellurene nanosheets (blue curve) show A_1 and E_2 modes at 124 and 144 cm^{-1} .⁵² The presence of the E_2 mode would suggest that the nanosheets are >20 nm thick (consistent with our AFM results) which is not active for monolayer or few-layer nanosheets.⁵³ For few-layer InSe (brown curve), the A_{1g} , E_{2g} , and another A_{1g} vibrational modes are identified at ~ 117 , 180, and 228 cm^{-1} , associated with out-of-plane and in-plane vibrations of Se and In atoms, respectively.¹⁹ All TMDs studied are consistent with previous reports of 2H semiconducting nanosheets since the J_1 , J_2 and J_3 vibrational modes attributed to the metallic 1T phase are not observed.^{36,37,39} The TMD alloy of $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ is shown in Supplementary Figure 21g (black curve) and we find the A_{1g} vibrational mode at ~ 247 cm^{-1} attributed to the out-of-plane motion of the Se atoms relative to a Mo or W atom and a weak E_{2g} vibration at ~ 146 cm^{-1} attributed to the in-plane vibrational motion of the Se atoms.³² HfSe_3 (green curve) shows a A_g peaks at 202 cm^{-1} , 232 cm^{-1} and 253 cm^{-1} , which are likely attributed to the A_g vibrational mode.⁵⁴ Supplementary Figure 21h presents a selection of the UV-visible optical absorption for tellurene, InSe, $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ and HfSe_3 inks, obtained using an integrating sphere where we have subtracted the scattering component of each spectrum from the extinction spectra.⁵⁸ The spectra of tellurene (blue curve) reveal an excitonic transition at 348 nm attributed to the transition of valence band p-orbital charge carriers to the conduction band.⁶⁰ The peak position is consistent with predicted density functional theory (DFT) values.^{60,84} The spectra of InSe (brown curve) show a broad peak at ~ 260 nm, consistent with the expected peak position from DFT calculations.⁶¹ The $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ spectra (black curve) show excitonic peaks similar to MoSe_2 (Supplementary Figure 16c) corresponding to the A and B excitons at 798 nm and 658 nm, respectively.⁶⁶ The spectra of HfSe_3 is shown as the green curve and show absorption peaks at 444 and 514 nm. To our knowledge, the optical properties of HfSe_3 nanosheets have not previously been examined. However the peaks may be related to the excitation of the charge carriers in the Se p-orbital valence states to the conduction band.⁷⁵ The UV-vis of all other inks are detailed in Supplementary Note 8-10. We estimate the inks' optical bandgap (E_{Op}) by plotting Tauc plots with absorption spectra (Supplementary Note 13). A straight line is extrapolated to the x-axis intercept to estimate E_{Op} . The E_{Op} is between 0.8 – 2.1 eV for most 2D inks except for TaS_2 , where the intercept is negative, likely due to the metallic properties of the material, therefore we assume $E_{\text{Op}} = 0$ eV since the E_f is in the conduction band. 2H- TaS_2 has previously shown metallic-like behaviour when electrochemically intercalated with ammonium cations⁸⁵ and the E_f is found in the conduction band.⁸⁶

Supplementary Figure 22: The elemental (black), TMM (yellow), TMD (blue) and TMT (green) crystals are plotted as a function of their aspect ratio after exfoliation and their interlayer spacing. We use interlayer spacings found from the XRD library from the International Centre for Diffraction Data.

We investigate the effect of the crystal interlayer spacing on the flake aspect ratio and find no correlation between the interlayer spacing and the aspect ratio of the flakes exfoliated shown in **Supplementary Figure 22** across the different families of 2D materials presented in **Supplementary Table 3**. We keep the intercalating ion diameter constant ($\text{TPA}^+ \approx 9.5 \text{ \AA}$) in all intercalations so that the mechanical properties could be changed and the aspect ratio measured. Materials such as HfSe_3 (interlayer spacing, $d = 9.34 \text{ \AA}$) and black phosphorous ($d = 2.06 \text{ \AA}$) have varied interlayer spacing but in both cases the flakes have large aspect ratio $\gg 30$. Furthermore, materials with large interlayer spacing such as InTe or GaTe (3-4 \AA) do not exfoliate well with $\text{AR} < 30$. Therefore, interlayer spacing is not a good metric for quantifying exfoliation success. We also find the interlayer spacing for each crystal is less than the TPA^+ cation diameter ($\approx 9.5 \text{ \AA}$) indicating that the cation must either elastically deform to enter the crystals or apply force to the outside of the crystals through electrostatic repulsion from other cations.

Material	$\langle AR \rangle$	Interlayer Spacing (Å)	E_{in}/E_{out}
BP	456 ± 81	2.064	1.9
Tellurene	9 ± 1	5.9	0.47
GaTe	3 ± 1	3.72	0.62
InSe	531 ± 74	4.16	1.72
InTe	6 ± 1	3.342	0.54
SnS	20 ± 9	3.2	0.55
SnSe	25 ± 8	2.93	0.87
MoSe ₂	250 ± 35	6.46	4.16
MoSe ₂ :Nb	212 ± 43	6.46	4.16
WSe ₂	67 ± 6	6.494	3.64
WSe ₂ :Nb	303 ± 57	6.494	3.64
MoS ₂	117 ± 20	6.155	5.18
Mo _{0.5} W _{0.5} Se ₂	188 ± 33	6.475	2.73
PtSe ₂	370 ± 78	5.08	5
WS ₂	347 ± 55	6.161	4.53
SnSe ₂	171 ± 21	6.137	3.27
TaS ₂	600 ± 115	6.05	3.78
NiPS ₃	2084 ± 448	6.34	2.81
CoPS ₃	198 ± 33	6.36	2.98
FePS ₃	160 ± 16	6.422	3.89
HfSe ₃	473 ± 72	9.34	2.81

Supplementary Table 3: Table of nanosheet aspect ratio, interlayer spacing and E_{in}/E_{out} values used.

Supplementary Figure 23: Transfer characteristics of GaTe and InTe. **a** Gate voltage sweep on GaTe nanosheet network with $V_{ds} = 0.5$ and 1 V. Gate leakage, I_g is shown as the green line. **b** Output characteristic of the GaTe device. **c** Gate voltage sweep on InTe nanosheet network with $V_{ds} = 0.5$ and 1 V. **d** Output characteristic of the InTe device.

We make solid-state devices using pre-patterned gold electrodes on Si/SiO₂ (90 nm SiO₂) (Fraunhofer Gen 4 OFET chips) which have much smaller $L_{CH} = 2.5$ μm ($W_{CH} = 10$ μm) than can be achieved with shadow mask evaporation, ideal for probing small $L < 500$ nm nanosheets. We drop cast GaTe and InTe into the substrates after EE in a glovebox in N₂. Exfoliation, centrifugation and washing protocols are the same as described in the main text. The nanosheets are of poor quality due to their low $E_{in}/E_{out} < 1$ and, therefore have low $AR = 3-6$, which is insufficiently high to create conformal nanosheet-to-nanosheet junctions. In Supplementary Figure 23, we plot the transfer characteristics for each material. Both InTe and GaTe show weak p-type behaviour which has not yet been reported for networks of solution processed nanosheets. The GaTe p-type behaviour has previously been reported for mechanical exfoliation of GaTe⁸⁷ and to our knowledge InTe transistors have not previously been reported. The average ambient μ_{NET} for the GaTe networks is $\mu_{GaTe} \approx 3.8 \times 10^{-7} \pm 7.6 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($N = 4$) and for InTe is $\mu_{InTe} \approx 1.7 \times 10^{-8} \pm 7.0 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($N = 4$). In both InTe and GaTe $I_{on}/I_{off} < 2$. In both GaTe and InTe the I_G current is several magnitudes (≈ 3 nA) below I_D , therefore we believe it is real modulation of the semiconductor, despite the low μ_{Net} obtained.

Supplementary Note 17 | Network Capacitance of Ionic Liquid Filled Networks

The areal capacitance (C_A) of a nanosheet network filled with ionic liquid will depend on various factors, including the voltage scan rate as shown in our previous work.⁶⁷ For an EE MoS₂ network (with the same nanosheet manufacturing process used in this article) with a network thickness, $t_{NET,MOS2} = 25$ nm and nanosheet thickness $t_{NS,MOS2} = 14$ nm, and using a CV scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹, we previously found $C_A = 3.1$ μF/cm².⁶⁷ However, C_A is dependent on both nanosheet thickness and network thickness because $C_A = C_V t_{Net}$ where C_V is the volumetric capacity of the network. In addition, it has been shown that $C_V \propto 1/t_{NS}$.⁸⁸ This is important here because, for our networks, t_{NET} varies between deposition methods. LS deposition can make ultra-thin networks < 20 nm however drop-casting often results in thicker films >50 nm due to poor control of the ink volume deposited. Thicker networks will inevitably have higher capacitance while thicker nanosheets will decrease C_A . In addition, our nanosheets have different thicknesses (t_{NS}) across materials. Therefore, we need to correct our C_A for each network using the information above which can be used to generate the equation,

$$C_A = C_{A,MOS2} \left(\frac{t_{NS,MOS2}}{t_{NS}} \right) \left(\frac{t_{NET}}{t_{NET,MOS2}} \right) \quad (3)$$

Material	t_{NS} (nm)	t_{NET} (nm)	C_A (μF/cm ²)
BP	7	50	12.40
Tellurene	43	550	22.20
GaTe	79	450	9.89
InSe	4	40	17.36
InTe	95	320	5.85
SnS	14	250	31.00
SnSe	23	350	26.42
MoSe ₂	10	28	4.86
MoSe ₂ :Nb	10	20	3.47
WSe ₂	9	30	5.79
WSe ₂ :Nb	5	25	8.68
MoS ₂	11	25	3.95
Mo _{0.5} W _{0.5} Se ₂	14	20	2.48
PtSe ₂	6	19	5.50
WS ₂	7	45	11.16
MoTe ₂	10	20	3.47
SnSe ₂	10	28	4.86
TaS ₂	3	50	28.93
NiPS ₃	4	50	21.70
CoPS ₃	15	170	19.67
FePS ₃	12	30	4.34
HfSe ₃	12	21	3.04

Supplementary **Table 4**: Table of nanosheet thickness, network thickness and network capacitance values.

We calculate μ_{NET} of the transistors from the equation $\mu_{NET} = (L_{CH}/W_{CH})(1/C_A)(g_m/V_{ds})$, where $g_m = \partial I_d/\partial V_g$ is the transconductance (e.g., measured from the slope of the transfer characteristic). μ_{peak} is found using the maximum value of the g_m . For the n-type and ambipolar materials the electron mobility is calculated and for the p-type materials the hole mobility is calculated.

We can compare our transistor μ_{NET} presented in Supplementary Table 5 to others in the literature for solution-processed networks. EE MoS₂ nanosheet networks have achieved $\mu_{Net} \sim 10 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $I_{on}/I_{off} \sim 10^6$ when made on silicon/silicon oxide (Si/SiO₂) substrates.⁸⁹ Other 2D nanosheet inks have also been used to make FETs. We have previously shown that tungsten disulfide (WS₂) and tungsten diselenide (WSe₂) have demonstrated n-type and ambipolar behaviour, respectively, achieving performances up to $\mu_{Net} \sim 10 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $I_{on}/I_{off} \sim 10^4$.⁶⁷ Platinum diselenide (PtSe₂) has demonstrated n-type behaviour on Si/SiO₂, achieving $\mu_{Net} \sim 0.004 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $I_{on}/I_{off} \sim 10^3$.⁹⁰ P-type behaviour has also been demonstrated with violet phosphorus (VP) achieving $\mu_{Net} \sim 2 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $I_{on}/I_{off} \sim 10^4$.⁹¹ EE BP field effect transistor (FET) with p-type behaviour have also been demonstrated on Si/SiO₂, achieving $\mu_{Net} \sim 0.002 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $I_{on}/I_{off} \sim 10^2$.⁹² Immersion of an EE WSe₂ network on Si/SiO₂ in iron trichloride (FeCl₃) and bromine (Br₂) solutions followed by annealing have been used to molecularly dope WSe₂ from its intrinsic ambipolar behaviour to a p-type nanosheet. The FET devices achieved performances of $\mu_{Net} \sim 1.5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $I_{on}/I_{off} \sim 10^6$ and $\mu_{Net} \sim 27 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $I_{on}/I_{off} \sim 10^7$ respectively.^{93,94} A further larger survey is conducted in the literature review of Supplementary Note 29. To our knowledge, we are the first to study the electrical properties of many of these materials with μ_{Net} comparable to state-of-the-art or reported for the first time.

Material	μ_{NET} (cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	μ_{peak} (cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	I_{on}/I_{off}	N	Comment
BP	$0.0008 \pm 4.7 \times 10^{-5}$	$0.0020 \pm 4.0 \times 10^{-4}$	76×10^1	12	
Tellurene	0.0012 ± 0.0010	0.002 ± 0.001	6×10^2	6	
GaTe	$3.8 \times 10^{-7} \pm 7.6 \times 10^{-8}$	-	< 2	4	
InSe	-	-	-	-	Too Insulating
InTe	$1.7 \times 10^{-8} \pm 7.0 \times 10^{-9}$	-	< 2	4	
SnS	-	-	-	-	Too Insulating
SnSe	-	-	-	-	Too Insulating
MoSe ₂	2.9 ± 0.4	5.4 ± 0.7	2×10^5	6	
MoSe ₂ :Nb	0.8 ± 0.04	2.2 ± 0.23	8×10^0	8	
WSe ₂	1.7 ± 0.2	2.6 ± 0.4	4×10^4	6	
WSe ₂ :Nb	2.0 ± 0.2	3.4 ± 0.2	3×10^3	7	
MoS ₂	8.4 ± 0.7	11.6 ± 1.2	2×10^3	9	
Mo _{0.5} W _{0.5} Se ₂	5.5 ± 0.9	13.2 ± 1.1	3×10^5	5	
PtSe ₂	1.1 ± 0.1	8.1 ± 1.5	5×10^2	5	
WS ₂	7.8 ± 0.8	13.3 ± 1.6	3×10^5	3	
MoTe ₂	2.3 ± 0.6	3.1 ± 0.7	7×10^4	7	
SnSe ₂	-	-	-	-	Metallic
TaS ₂	-	-	-	-	Metallic
NiPS ₃	-	-	-	-	Too Insulating
CoPS ₃	-	-	-	-	Too Insulating
FePS ₃	-	-	-	-	Too Insulating
HfSe ₃	-	-	-	-	Too Insulating

Supplementary **Table 5**: Table of network mobility, peak mobility, on/off ratio and sample amount of each ionically gated network.

Supplementary Figure 24: Transfer curve of each nanosheet network used to make ionically gated transistors. Ionic current (dashed red line) of each ionically gated transistor, which is consistent with the conductivity of EMIM-TFSI found in previous work.⁶⁷

Supplementary Note 19 | Output Characteristics of Ionic Gated Transistors

Supplementary Figure 25: Output curves of the n-type ionic gated transistors showing the highest drain current at positive gate voltages. We attribute the current offset at 0 V to the ionic liquid current.

Supplementary Figure 26: Output curves of the ambipolar ionic gated transistors showing the highest drain current at positive and negative gate voltages. We attribute the current offset at 0 V to the ionic liquid current.

Supplementary Figure 27: Output curves of the p-type gated transistors showing the highest drain current at negative gate voltages. We attribute the current offset at 0 V to the ionic liquid current.

Supplementary Figure 28: Summary of the network conductivity (σ_{Net}) and charge carrier density (n) for each nanosheet network.

The network conductivity of our nanosheet networks is directly proportional to the number of charge carriers available to transport electric charge, n which can be understood through $\sigma_{\text{Net}} = nq\mu_{\text{Net}}$, where q is the charge of the carriers. Since the network μ_{NET} is now known from our transistors, we can calculate n for each network, assuming μ_{NET} is independent of n , as shown in Supplementary Figure 28. We observe an increase in n with σ_{NET} since more charge carriers are available to conduct current. Our niobium-doped WSe₂ and MoSe₂ have the highest $n \sim 10^{24} - 10^{27} \text{ m}^{-3}$ as expected and similar in magnitude to previous mechanically exfoliated niobium-doped TMDs.⁹⁵ As a consequence of their high n , niobium-doped WSe₂ and MoSe₂ devices suffer from charge carrier screening of the gate's electric field and suffer from low $I_{\text{on}}/I_{\text{off}}$ ratio $\sim 10^2$. PtSe₂ and MoS₂ are unlike the other EE semiconductors since they have a high $n \sim 10^{23} \text{ m}^{-3}$. MoS₂ is the only natural 2D crystal we have used for the article, and it is likely that the crystal is unintentionally doped with rhenium before it is mined.⁹⁶ Even in dilute concentrations (<1 at.%) it can drastically n-dope the MoS₂ and increase n .⁹⁷ A high n would explain why I_{off} is high ($\sim 1 \mu\text{A}$) even in literature solid-state devices, resulting in a low $I_{\text{on}}/I_{\text{off}}$. Torsi *et. al* have also observed that V_{th} is shifted towards negative voltages⁹⁷ with Re doping, which is widely seen for the majority of solution-processed literature (Supplementary Note 29). PtSe₂ electrical properties are highly dependent on its layer thickness, it is a semiconductor up to 3 atomic layers but a semimetal for >3 layers ($t > 5 \text{ nm}$).⁹⁸ We find $\langle t \rangle = 6 \pm 1 \text{ nm}$ for our EE ink (Supplementary Note 3), which is a composite of thick (>10 nm) and thin (1 nm) nanosheets. Therefore, we have a combination of semiconducting and semi-metallic properties, resulting in a high n . We find that the elemental materials (BP and tellurene) are also outliers in Supplementary Figure 28, possibly due to an underestimation of their mobility. Tellurene is a low AR material ($AR = 9$) (Supplementary Note 3), while BP has a puckered structure forbidding the formation of conformal junctions.^{78,99} Additionally, BP and tellurene are not air stable,^{100,101} therefore it is possible that oxidation reduced the effective μ_{NET} in the devices.

1) OPTP measurements

We obtain an approximation of the real THz conductivity averaged over the frequency with OPTP measurements. The sum of the products of the quantum yields of electrons and holes and their respective (real) mobilities are obtained according to

$$S_{approx}(\tau) = \Phi_e(\tau)\mu_e + \Phi_h(\tau)\mu_h = \frac{\epsilon_0 c (n_f + n_b)}{e N_a} \left[\frac{E^{off}(t_{max}) - E^{on}(t_{max}, \tau)}{E^{on}(t_{max}, \tau)} \right]. \quad (4)$$

Here, τ is the delay time between the optical pump pulse and the time at which the THz conductivity is determined, N_a is photoexcitation density per unit area (2×10^{12} - 8×10^{12} photons cm^{-2}), ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, c is the speed of light, while n_f and n_b are the refractive indices of the media in front and back of the sample, respectively. The samples are photoexcited with pump photon energy of 3.1 eV, which is well above the bandgap of the TMDs studied and thus leads to initially hot charge carriers. The hot charges can energetically relax to the band edges by phonon emission and decay via recombination to neutral excitons or entrapment at defects. We assume that the energetic relaxation to the band edges occurs within 5 ps.

2) TRTS measurements

TRTS is a more accurate measurement than OPTP and provides the sum of the products of the quantum yields of electrons and holes and their respective (real) mobilities as a function of the radian probe frequency, ω . We measure the THz wave forms $E^{off}(t)$ and $E^{on}(t, \tau)$ as a function of the THz delay time, t , and calculate their Fourier transforms to obtain the frequency dependent results according to

$$S(\omega, \tau) = \Phi_e(\tau)\mu_e(\omega) + \Phi_h(\tau)\mu_h(\omega) = \frac{c \epsilon_0 (n_f + n_b)}{e N_a} \frac{E^{off}(\omega, \tau) - E^{on}(\omega, \tau)}{E^{on}(\omega, \tau)}. \quad (5)$$

. Figure 4a of the main text shows the sum of the products of the quantum yields of electrons and holes and their respective mobilities as a function of frequency, as obtained from TRTS measurements and eq. 5. In the main text we define the nanosheet mobility as $\mu_{NS}(\omega, \tau) = S(\omega, \tau)$. The μ_{NS} at 1 THz and $\tau = 5$ ps is found to be 75, 61, 51, 42, 38, 32, 26 for WSe₂, WS₂, MoSe₂, MoS₂, Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂, WSe₂:Nb and MoSe₂:Nb, respectively. For the PtSe₂ sample the OPTP measurements showed a rapid decay within a few picoseconds, therefore we determined the nanosheet mobility from TRTS at $\tau = 2$ ps, which is equal to $18 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.

Supplementary Figure 29: Real (left) and imaginary (right) part of the impedance of a nanosheet junction pair, measured for different networks. The curves are fitted using a modified equation for the Randles circuit presented in our previous work.¹⁰²

We have recently demonstrated that A.C. impedance spectroscopy allows R_J , R_{NS} , to be measured simultaneously with μ_{NS} and μ_{NET} indirectly estimated by leveraging the capacitance of the junctions between nanosheets.¹⁰² The network impedance, Z_{Net} , is converted into the impedance of the average nanosheet-junction pair, Z_{NS-J} . The Z_{NS-J} spectrum is then fitted with an equivalent circuit model of a Randle's circuit to yield values of R_{NS} , R_J for networks of MoS₂, WS₂, MoSe₂ and MoSe₂:Nb. The real component of Z_{NS-J} is shown in Supplementary Figure 29 (left) while the imaginary component of Z_{NS-J} is shown on the right. At low frequency, the real impedance, $\text{Re}(Z_{NS-J})$ is equal to $R_J + R_{NS}$ and as the frequency approaches infinity, the impedance will equal R_{NS} .

Supplementary Figure 30: Measurement of contact resistance. Series resistance R_s as a function of the channel length on networks of MoS₂, MoSe₂, MoSe₂:Nb and WS₂.

We use impedance spectroscopy to extract the series resistance R_s our equivalent circuit model of a Randel's circuit, since the contact resistance, R_c will appear as a contribution to the series resistance. We follow the protocol established in our previous work¹⁰² to extract R_s and R_l and then plot R_s vs channel length in Supplementary Figure 30 for MoS₂, MoSe₂, MoSe₂:Nb and WS₂ networks. We find the percentage change of the R_s component (ΔR_s) between the high (30Mhz) and low (20 Hz) frequency regimes for each channel length. For MoS₂, WS₂ and MoSe₂ the $\Delta R_s \sim 7$ -50%, while for MoSe₂:Nb the $\Delta R_s \sim 80\%$. The intercept is then $2R_c$ as in the case of the transfer length method to measure contact resistance. The channel width in each case is 19.4 mm. Therefore, we find the contact resistance is 3.2 MΩ μm, 2.9 MΩ μm, 3.7 MΩ μm and 1.0 MΩ μm for MoS₂, MoSe₂, WS₂ and MoSe₂:Nb respectively.

Supplementary Figure 31: **a** Transfer characteristic of WS₂ FET used for the DAC circuits. The gate leakage is shown as the purple line. **b** Transfer characteristic of Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ FET used for the NMOS and BASK circuits. The gate leakage is shown as the purple line. **c** Transfer characteristic of the Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ driver FET and load FET used in the NMOS circuit. The gate leakage current is shown in the inset. **d** NMOS inverter using solution-processed Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ (schematic inset) and its static voltage transfer characteristic when the supply voltage, $V_{DD} = 1.5$ V. The blue line shows the input voltage (V_{IN}) versus output voltage (V_{OUT}), with the voltage gain depicted by the orange line.

Digital integrated circuits (IC's) rely on complementary semiconductor materials metal-oxide-semiconductor (MOS) technology that uses p-type (PMOS logic) or n-type (NMOS logic) FETs to implement mixed-signal ICs and logic gates.¹⁰³ Figures of merit such as switching speed (τ), and inverter voltage gain ($|A_v|$), defined as the slope of the inverter voltage transfer characteristic (dV_{OUT}/dV_{IN} , where V_{IN} is the input and V_{OUT} the output voltage), have been used to assess and benchmark the performance of the FETs and ICs. Solution-

processed 2D logic has only started within the last few years. The first complementary inverters with solution-processed LPE graphene/hexagonal boron nitride heterostructures achieved an inverter voltage gain, $|A_v| \approx 0.1$ and could not amplify an input voltage, V_{in} since the graphene channel lacked E_g .¹⁰⁴ Lin et al. then demonstrated NMOS with spin-coated MoS₂ achieving $|A_v| \approx 20$.⁸⁹ Inkjet-printed CMOS logic was then demonstrated using MoS₂ as an n-type material and organic polymer as a p-type material, achieving $|A_v| \approx 1.4$.¹⁰⁵ This was an essential step as it was the first time an input signal could be successfully amplified in a complementary circuit. The CMOS also had fast $\tau \approx 3.5 \mu\text{s}$ that was limited by the poor conductivity of the channel with very high contact resistance, $R_c > 600 \text{ M}\Omega \mu\text{m}$.¹⁰⁵ Ricciardulli et al. demonstrated an all-2D CMOS using drop-cast p-type VP and n-type MoS₂ achieving $|A_v| \approx 17$ however, τ was several milliseconds since ionic liquid was used to gate the devices.⁹¹ More recently, n-type MoS₂ and p-type Br-doped WSe₂ have been drop cast on Si/SiO₂ and patterned by photolithography to achieve a remarkable $|A_v| \approx 1280$ demonstrating that it is possible to make high-performance logic with solution-processed 2D materials.⁹⁴ Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ FETs have yet to be used to implement solution processed logic devices.

We use e-beam lithography to pattern Ti/Au (3/37 nm) source and drain electrodes and Al (40 nm) gate electrodes onto Si/SiO₂ substrates. A native AlO_x layer, approximately 4 nm thick, formed by exposing Al to ambient air, serves as the gate dielectric in our solid-state FETs. LS deposition is then used to deposit networks ($t \approx 25 \text{ nm}$) of Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ onto the electrodes to complete the device arrays (See Supporting Information S1).

In Supplementary Figure 31a and Supplementary Figure 31b we obtain transfer characteristics of the FETs with channel geometry $L_{CH} = 10 \mu\text{m}$ and $W_{CH} = 200 \mu\text{m}$ (WS₂) and $W_{CH} = 300 \mu\text{m}$ (Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂) and drain voltage V_{DS} of 0.01 and 0.5 V. Additionally, in Supplementary Figure 31c we show the transfer characteristic of the Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ FETs used in the NMOS for the driver and load FETs using $V_{DS} = 0.1 \text{ V}$. The gate voltage (V_{GS}) is swept at $\pm 2 \text{ V}$, sufficient to switch the FETs between on and off states due to the high oxide capacitance of the AlO_x dielectric, $C_{ox} \sim 1.4 \mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$. The transfer curves for the WS₂ and Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ devices showed minimal hysteresis, which was attributed to a dielectric/semiconductor interface with minimal trap sites. We observe n-type behaviour for the WS₂ and Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂. The p-type component of the transfer characteristic for Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ is likely at lower $V_{GS} < -2 \text{ V}$. Since an ultra-thin AlO_x layer of $\sim 4 \text{ nm}$ is used, it is not possible to sweep to a larger V_{GS} range without increasing the gate leakage beyond I_D . We find $\mu_j \sim 0.1 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the WS₂ and Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ FETs, lower than the ionic transistors described in the main text. We attribute the lower μ_j to overestimating the active channel width since the current will only pass through some nanosheets in the network, as shown in our previous works by conductive AFM.¹⁰⁵ Additionally, the FETs likely suffer from a high contact resistance $R_c \sim 1 \text{ M}\Omega \mu\text{m}$ as shown with WS₂, MoSe₂ and MoSe₂:Nb networks in Supplementary Note 23.

We make an n-channel metal–oxide–semiconductor (NMOS) inverter using Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ shown in the schematic of Supplementary Figure 31d (inset) using the top FET as a depletion load and the bottom FET as

the driver. The latter actively switches the circuit between its high and low states based on the input voltage, V_{IN} . The static voltage transfer characteristic of the NMOS inverter is shown by the blue line in Supplementary Figure 31d. When the $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ gate has V_{IN} lower than the threshold voltage V_{th} of the driver FET, the driver FET is off and the voltage drop across the depletion load is small, thus the output voltage (V_{OUT}) is high ($V_{OUT} \approx V_{DD}$). As V_{IN} increases and exceeds V_{th} , the driver FET turns on and V_{OUT} will drop to the logic low state, achieving signal inversion with a voltage gain $|A_{v,NMOS}| \approx 4$ (orange line), comparable to previous EE MoS_2 NMOS circuits.^{89,105}

Supplementary Figure 32: **a** Schematic of the circuit to measure the RC time constant with an $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ FET. The gate was connected to a function generator providing a square wave gate potential. The AP load is $R_{AP} = 1 \text{ M}\Omega$ with a capacitance, $C_{AP} = 1 \text{ pF}$. **b** D.C. transfer curve of the $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ FET.

The time constant in a circuit comprising a single $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ FET is measured by connecting an active probe (AP) directly to the drain of the FET, as shown in the circuit schematic in Supplementary Figure 32a. The AP functions as a load resistor (R_{AP}) in D.C. conduction. The drain current $I_D = I_R + I_C$, where $I_R = -V_D/R_{AP}$ is the resistive and $I_C = -C_{AP} dV_D/dt$ is the capacitive component of the current. I_D can be noisy because of the derivative term therefore it is more practical to use V_{DS} to calculate the time constant, τ . In Supplementary Figure 32b the D.C. transfer curve was derived using the equation $V_{DS} = V_{SS} - R_{AP} \cdot I_D$ where $V_{SS} = 0.5 \text{ V}$ is the supply voltage provided by the Keithley 2636B source-measure unit. $V_{GS,low}$ and $V_{GS,high}$ are the levels of the input square wave where $V_{GS} = V_G + V_{SS}$. The corresponding V_{DS} levels are $V_{DS,high}$ and $V_{DS,low}$ which are the steady-state levels of the V_{DS} vs. time waveforms shown in Supplementary Figure 33.

Supplementary Figure 33: **a** Steady-state waveforms of the V_{GS} input (red curve) and V_{DS} (blue curve) at a frequency of 2.5 kHz. **b** Steady-state waveforms of the V_{GS} input with a different time base.

Supplementary Figure 34: The response of V_{DS} to applied V_{GS} as a function of time. **a** The switching time τ_r measured for a rising V_{DS} signal. **b** The switching time τ_f measured for a falling V_{DS} signal.

We magnify the response of V_{DS} in Supplementary Figure 34. The rise time of V_{DS} is longer than the fall time, indicating two different switching time constants, τ . From the exponential fit of the rising V_{DS} (Supplementary Figure 34a) and falling V_{DS} (Supplementary Figure 34b) the rising, τ_r and falling, τ_f switching time of the circuit can be found respectively. We find $\tau_r = 12.8 \mu s$ and $\tau_f = 2.6 \mu s$ indicating the fast response of the $Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se_2$ FETs, which is comparable to previously reported EE MoS_2 FETs which achieved $\tau = 3.3 \mu s$.

Supplementary Figure 35: **a** Circuit diagram of the analog-to-digital converter connected with 3 bits to the solution-processed DAC where a logic table is also shown. **b** Digital signals from bit lines in a 3-bit DAC, showing the contribution of each digital signal to the output voltage. **c** Analog output (V_{OUT}) of the WS₂ 3-bit DAC compared to the input (V_{IN}) triangle wave, showing pulsed signal due to ADC operation. Analog input to the ADC (orange line) and the corresponding analog output (purple line) from the 3-bit WS₂ DAC.

We use the solution-processed DAC to restore an analogue signal as shown in the circuit diagram of Supplementary Figure 35a. We input an analog triangle wave, V_{IN} , into a conventional Si AD7819 analog-to-digital converter (ADC), which outputs a digital signal of logic "1" or "0" to the WS₂ DAC. We first make a 3-bit DAC and connect the ADC to the DAC using bit lines (b_2 , b_1 and b_0), where each bit represents a power of 2 in binary weighting. In our 3-bit DAC, b_2 represents the most significant bit and b_0 represents the least significant bit. We define V_{DD} as the power supply voltage of the ADC. If the value of a bit line is "1", the corresponding ADC output will go to the value of V_{DD} and if it is "0" the output will go to ground. Supplementary Figure 35b shows the digital signals of bits b_2 (red), b_1 (green), and b_0 (blue), and the corresponding binary weighted integer N . We achieve these weights by summing the contribution of each digital signal to the output voltage, V_{OUT} , of the DAC. The contribution of each signal is halved for each node going to the output. For example, in a 3-bit DAC, the contribution of b_2 is halved once, b_1 twice and b_0 three times. The formula for the output voltage considering each bit can influence the voltage by its weighted proportion of the total V_{DD} is, $V_{OUT} = 2^{-n} \times V_{DD} \times N$, where n is the number of bit lines. For our 3-bit DAC, $n = 3$ and V_{DD} is set to 5 V.

In Supplementary Figure 35c, we show the V_{IN} (orange) to the ADC and the analog output of the WS₂ DAC (purple line). V_{OUT} is a pulsed signal due to the operation of the ADC. The ADC performs a digital conversion at the beginning of each non-gray interval. During this time, the ADC is busy, and its digital outputs are at 0 V, hence $V_{OUT} = 0$ V. We set the sampling period to 6.25 ms to get 16 sampling intervals within 100 ms, which is the period of the input triangle wave (orange line). Since the sampling is done asynchronously with respect to the input signal, V_{OUT} is offset in time to V_{IN} .

Supplementary Figure 36: a Circuit diagram of the analog-to-digital converter connected with 4 bits to the solution-processed DAC where a logic table is also shown where $V_{DD} = 5$ V. **b** Analog output of the WS₂ 4-bit DAC compared to the input triangle wave, showing pulsed signal due to ADC operation. Analog input to the ADC (orange line) and the corresponding analog output (purple line) from the 4-bit WS₂ DAC.

We make solution processed 4-bit WS₂ DACs to build on the work of the 3-bit DAC's presented in the main text. In Supplementary Figure 36a we show the circuit diagram of the 4-bit DAC adding one extra binary weighted resistor to give 16 discrete V_{OUT} values shown in the logic table (hexadecimal encoding is used for N). In Supplementary Figure 36b, we show the V_{IN} (orange) to the ADC and the analog output of the WS₂ DAC (purple line). V_{OUT} is a pulsed signal due to the operation of the ADC. We set the sampling period to 3.125 ms to get 32 sampling intervals within 100 ms, which is the period of the input triangle wave (orange line). Since the sampling is done asynchronously with respect to the input signal, V_{OUT} is offset in time to V_{IN} . The quantisation is not perfectly symmetrical in the 4-bit DAC, which we attribute to the network's non-identical WS₂ resistances between semiconductor channels.

Supplementary Figure 37: **a** Circuit diagram of the $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ solution processed BASK circuit (top) and example binary input required to encode "Politecnico" and "Dublin" in 7-bit ASCII (bottom). **b** The clock signal with a frequency of $f_{CLK} = 100 \text{ Hz}$ is shown by the green curve, while the V_{IN} represents the digital message shown by the blue curve. The local oscillator V_{LO} is shown in red. The output of the BASK circuit V_{BASK} which has the encoded digital message in the local oscillator is shown by the orange curve and the demodulated BASK signal V_{Demod} is shown as the purple line.

We expand our work on $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ FETs to implement BASK circuits to modulate the amplitude of a high-frequency signal by a binary signal obtained by encoding a message. The modulated signal is demodulated using an amplitude modulation (AM) demodulator. The circuit diagram is shown in Supplementary Figure 37a. ASCII is a standard way of representing characters as binary numbers. As an example, Supplementary Figure 37a shows the binary bits required to encode "Politecnico" and "Dublin". The digital message "Politecnico di Milano and University of Dublin" was encoded using 7-bit ASCII. Since each character is represented by 7 bits and the message has 46 characters, the total number of bits sent is $46 \text{ characters} \times 7 \text{ bits/character} = 322 \text{ bits}$. The encoded binary sequence (322 bits) of high "1" and low "0" is input as V_{IN} to the top FET of the BASK modulator. The green curve in Supplementary Figure 37b represents the clock signal with a frequency of $f_{CLK} = 100 \text{ Hz}$ which each period corresponds to the transmission of one bit of data. Therefore we have a data transmission rate of 100 bits a second (bps). We provide a high-frequency (1 kHz) AC sine wave, with an amplitude of 200 mV, to act as a carrier signal denoted as the local oscillator, V_{LO} . The BASK circuit then converts the binary sequency into an AM signal previously represented as V_{OUT}

which we will now call V_{BASK} shown as the orange curve of Supplementary Figure 37b. V_{BASK} is input into the AM demodulator and the output voltage is denoted as V_{Demod} shown by the purple line of Supplementary Figure 37b. Supplementary Figure 37b (orange and purple curves) shows a short part (175 milliseconds) of the modulated and demodulated signal. The entire message takes 3.22 seconds to transmit (322 bits/100 bps) and the snippet of the signal shows how the signal behaves to transmit a space and the letter "U".

Supplementary Figure 38: **a** Eye diagram of the demodulated BASK signal, the horizontal axis represents time (2 ms/div), while the vertical axis represents the demodulated signal (20 mV/div). **b** The clock signal (green), V_{IN} (blue), V_{LO} (red), V_{BASK} (orange) and V_{Demod} (purple) at a shorter time window than in Supplementary Figure 37 using the same device.

We show an eye diagram in Supplementary Figure 38a which is tool typically used in digital communications to visualize how well a digital signal can be interpreted by the receiver. Supplementary Figure 38a is obtained from the entire modulated message (all 322 bits). Supplementary Figure 38b shows the same plot and device as Supplementary Figure 37 but with a time window between 100 and 150 ms to see the demodulated signal more clearly. The clear, open eye pattern in Supplementary Figure 38a indicates a good quality signal with minimal interference and noise.

Supplementary Note 29 | Literature Review of Solution Processed 2D Materials

Deposition Method	Material	Annealing Temperature (°C)	Acid Treatment (TFSI)	Measurement Environment	Mobility $\text{cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$	$I_{\text{on}}/I_{\text{off}}$	Year	Method	Ref
Spin Coating	MoS ₂ rGO	50 C (overnight)	No	Ambient	0.3	<2	2012	LPE	106
Inkjet Printing	MoS ₂	450C 1 hours	No	Passivation (ALD 50nm Al ₂ O ₃)	0.00048	3	2014	LPE	107
Spin Coating TiO ₂ /drop casting MoS ₂	MoS ₂	250C for TiO ₂ - 25 C	No	10 ⁻⁶ mBar (for 12 h)	0.02	nan	2014	LPE	108
Dip-Coating	MoS ₂	350 C 1 hour	Yes hydrazine hydrate	Ambient	0.4	10 ⁶	2015	Chemical	109
Inkjet/Spray/Evaporation	MoS ₂ /WS ₂ /WSe ₂ /MoSe ₂	70 C 24 hours	No	Under Vacuum (1 x 10 ⁻⁴ mbar)	0.1	100	2017	LPE	110
Inkjet Printing	Graphene, hBN	100C 1 hour	no	Ambient Air	204	2.5	2017	LPE	104
Drop-casting	Few-layer BP	250 (in forming gas H ₂ /Ar)	Not specified	Ambient	Up to 100 (60 on average), as single nanosheets (not a network)	~1 × 10 ⁴ (avg.)	2018	EE	111
Spin-coating	MoS ₂	300 C	Yes	Vacuum	7-11	10 ⁶	2018	EE	89
Spray	WS ₂	100C for 12h	No	Under Vacuum <10 ⁻⁶ mbar	0.01	10 ⁴	2018	LPE	112
Spray Coating	MoS ₂	200C for 2 hours	No	nan	0.0004	22	2018	LPE	113
Spray Coating	InSe	200 °C for 30 minutes	Not specified	Under vacuum	3 × 10 ⁻⁵	3	2020	na	114
Liquid-Liquid Assembly	MoS ₂	200 C for 2 hours	No	Ambient	0.73	10 ⁵	2020	EE	79

Spray Coating + ebeam evaporation	WSe ₂	80C + 70C overnight	No	Under Vacuum	0.08 (WSe ₂), 0.1 (WS ₂)	10 ³	2020	LPE	115
Electrohydrodynamic Jet	MoS ₂	150 (pre-annealing), 1000	No	Not mentioned	19.4	5.0×10 ⁶	2021	Pre-cursor solution	116
Unknown	In ₂ Se ₃	400C	Not specified	In vacuum and dark	0.2	10 ⁵	2021	EE	117
Inkjet Printing	MoS ₂	200 (in air) followed by 300 (in argon atmosphere)	Not specified	Ambient	Subthermionic: Not specified; Thermionic: 7-11	Subthermionic: up to 10 ⁶ ; Thermionic: up to 10 ⁶	2021	Chemical	118
Spray Coating	GaSe	Not Specified	Not Applicable	Ambient	≈10 ⁻³	≈10 ³	2021	LPE	119
Spin-coating	MoS ₂	250C 1.5h + 400C 2 hours	nan	Vacuum	5	10 ⁶	2021	EE	120
Inkjet Printing + ALD + e-beam	MoS ₂	400C 1 hour	No	Ambient	0.1	25	2021	EE	121
Inkjet Printing + ALD + e-beam	MoS ₂	400C 1 hour	Yes	Ambient	0.06	50	2021	EE	105
Drop Casting - MoS ₂ / Dry transfer from PET	MoS ₂	110C + 90C for 30min	Yes, saturated solution of BDT	Under Vacuum <10 ⁻⁶ mbar	0.01	10 ⁴	2021	LPE	122
Spin Coating + photolithography	MoS ₂	80C	Yes (TFSI)	Under Vacuum (~7 × 10 ⁻⁵ torr)	1.8	10 ⁶	2021	EE	123
Spin-Coated	MoS ₂	1000 °C for 1h	No	(~10 ⁻² Torr) growth only	7.9	10 ⁵	2021	Chemical	124
Spin Coating + wet transfer + inkjet printing - Inkjet not used for dielectric	MoS ₂ /HfS ₂	500C for 5h (HfO ₂), 80C for 5min (MoS ₂), 100C for 5min (TFSI).	Yes (TFSI)	All under vacuum (10 ⁻⁵ Torr)	8.3	10 ⁶	2021	EE	125

		300C for 30min + 200C for 30min							
Inkjet Printing	MoS ₂	500 (for HfO ₂)	Yes (TFSI for MoS ₂)	Not mentioned	~10	>10 ⁵	2022	EE	126
Layer-by-Layer (LbL) assembly	In ₂ Se ₃	200°C (Vacuum for 2 hours before the test)	Not mentioned directly	Not mentioned directly	Single nanosheet: 12.8 cm ² /Vs, Thin film: 0.4 cm ² /Vs	Single nanosheet: > 1.5 × 10 ³ , Thin film: 7 × 10 ⁴	2022	EE	127
Drop-casting	Violet Phosphorus	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	2.25	10 ⁴	2022	LPE	91
Direct Writing	MoS ₂	300	Not applicable	Ambient	Up to 6.7	2 × 10 ⁶	2022	EE	128
Spin coating	Graphene, MoS ₂ , HfO ₂ from HfS ₂	500 (for HfS ₂ to HfO ₂ conversion)	Yes	Room temperature, under vacuum	8.3 for MoS ₂ devices	1.6 × 10 ⁶ for MoS ₂ devices	2022	EE	125
Screen Printing	WSe ₂	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Room Temperature	0.066	≈2000	2022	LPE	129
Langmuir Shafer/Stamping	MoS ₂	200C for 2 hours	no	Under N ₂	0.2	14	2022	EE with Powder	130
Spin-coated Mos ₂ +wet transfer	MoS ₂	300C	no	no	10	100	2022	EE	131
Vacuum filtration transfer	BP	nan	nan	nan	0.002	130	2022	EE	92
Slot-Die Coating	MoS ₂	250	Yes	Not Mentioned	~112	>10 ⁵	2023	EE	132
Inkjet Printing	MoS ₂ & Graphene	350	Not explicitly mentioned but TFSI treatment discussed	Ambient	≈0.27 (for AlOx/Si substrate), potentially higher due to actual channel	Up to 10 ³ (AlOx/Si substrate)	2023	EE	133

			as a method for enhancing mobility		width considerations				
Drop-casting	WSe ₂ , MoS ₂ (for complementary circuits)	200 (for annealing in a nitrogen-filled glovebox)	Not specified	Measurements in an N ₂ -filled glovebox at 25°C, bias stress measurement at 60°C under vacuum	>27	~10 ⁷	2023	EE	94
Unknown, likely dropcast	PtSe ₂	Not specified	Not specified	Vacuum at room temperature	0.0004 (n-type behavior attributed to Se vacancies)	6.3 × 10 ³	2023	EE	90
Langmuir–Schaefer coating	MoS ₂ , WS ₂ , WSe ₂	120	Not used	Ambient	MoS ₂ : ≈ 11, WS ₂ : ≈ 9, WSe ₂ : ≈ 2	MoS ₂ : ≈ 2.6 × 10 ³ , WS ₂ : ≈ 3.4 × 10 ³ , WSe ₂ : ≈ 4.2 × 10 ⁴	2023	EE	67
Drop-casting	WSe ₂	Not directly mentioned; annealed at 80°C for FeCl ₃ doping	FeCl ₃ (p-type doping)	Ambient	~1.5 after FeCl ₃ doping	~10 ⁶	2023	EE	93
Inkjet Printed MoS ₂ and ionic gel	MoS ₂	200C 1 hour, Ar atmosphere at 120°C	Yes (TFSI, 80C 1 hour)	No	11	10 ⁶	2023	EE	134
Drop-casting	MoSe ₂	120-180	No	N ₂ -filled glovebox	1.5	>10 ⁶	2024	EE	135
Drop-casting	WS ₂	120-180	No	N ₂ -filled glovebox	0.6	>10 ⁶	2024	EE	135
Not mentioned	WSe ₂	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	0.002	~10 ²	2024	EE	135

Not mentioned	MoS ₂	Not mentioned	Yes	Not mentioned	0.5	3	2024	EE	135
Langmuir–Blodgett and spin-coating	MoS ₂ and Sr _{1.8} Bi _{0.2} Nb ₃ O ₁₀	Below 250	Yes, bis(trifluoromethane)sulfonimide (TFSI) treatment	Ambient air	Average 4.4, Maximum 11	>10 ⁵	2024	EE	136
Drop Casting	MoS ₂	15 min at 120 °C in an Ar glovebox	no	Ambient Air	15	26	2024	EE	80
Drop Casting	WSe ₂	15 min at 120 °C in an Ar glovebox	no	Ambient Air	1	10 ⁴	2024	EE	80
Langmuir–Schaefer coating	MoS ₂	150	No	Ambient	≈ 7	10 ³	2024	EE	102

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